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Investigating The Transformations Of An Educational Institution In Greece: Model - Experimental Schools (MES)

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During the 19th century in Greece, Model Schools for Boys were founded and operated as National Schools. In the 1920s the experimental schools of the University of Athens and Thessaloniki were founded as well. After several years, in 1936, more than a hundred secondary schools were established as Model Schools (Selective Schools). All historical Model Schools operated according to this new institution. Some new schools were added until 1972. The selection of students in these schools was by examinations in academics. The 1985 is the year of conversion of all Model Schools into Experimental with different orientation. The acceptance of students was taking place by lottery, not by examination. The year of 2011 is the one of transformation of these schools into Model-Experimental Schools (MES), ie an attempt to reconcile the characteristics of various types of schools founded, developed and transformed during the last two centuries in the country.

The law of 2011 establishing the MES has been based on four pillars:

- a. educational excellence and creativity,
- b. experimentation, innovation, educational research and the dissemination of good practices in the rest of the system,
- c. systematic evaluation of teachers, students, functions and structures and
- d. the innovations in the management of schools.

In the spirit of this law, a network of schools of all levels is invited to play this "role-model" for the entire educational system of the country. The old examination system was returned for the selection of students, modeled on the old Model Schools.

The creation of Model Schools, Experimental Schools, Schools of "excellence" etc. have come in most EU countries. The existence of social inequalities in several countries (Duru-Bellat, Van Zanten, 2009), the development of structures of "excellence", giving relatively unsatisfactory results (Duru-Bellat, Van Zanten, 2002) and the greater socialization through these structures has been identified and recorded (Van Zanten, 2014) in France since many years. However, this effort is disputed as capable to serve policy against inequality (Allouch and Van Zanten, 2008). In England after 1960, progressive changes for innovation and experimentation become in a violent and unplanned manner (Hagreaves, 2000). Over time, however, schools supported in selecting students (Grammar Schools), were questioned and most of them were closed or converted into Comprehensive Schools (McCulloch and Crook, 2013).

We have found while traditionally Model and Experimental Schools in Greece, had been separated structures, however, with the recent legislation a paradox was attempted: how to combine the two into one structure. In the ranking given in these schools in 2011, based on criteria adapted to current perceptions of education, the MES occupied positions rather not in proportion to the traditional way of development of schools in Greece. And this seems problematic. Schools that were founded in the 19th century with the longest tradition and history did not take the leading positions of the evaluation list. However, they have the highest percentage of demand in relation to the positions they offer. We probably have a formed social collective imaginary (Castoriadis, 1999) in the educational community, which acts independently of the legal framework of these schools.

This research in a first level of macro-analysis tries to highlight subtle aspects of the special status of these schools. Their differentiation compared to other schools, experimentation, innovation, the "excellence" and the demand and expectations of the parents of these schools are issues to be investigated.

At a second level of micro-analysis the research expects to reveal the existence of a different educational social collective imaginary through social meanings and the meanings attached by subjects to what relates to the educational process and the common values espoused by them (Angus, 1986).

Methodology, Methods, Research Instruments or Sources Used

In this qualitative research we use a mixed method approach in order to highlight the special situation of Model – Experimental Schools in Greece and to reveal the differentiation in the educational collective social imaginary inside this institution depending on the history and earlier operation of each school as selective or experimental.

This research is based on critical narrative analysis combined with an ethnographic approach. Critical Narrative Analysis combines Critical Discourse Analysis and narrative analysis in order to allow us to learn how people create their selves in constant social interactions at both personal and institutional levels, and how institutional discourses influence and are influenced by personal everyday narratives (Souto-Manning, 2014). We will try to connect the institution of MES with the socio-historical composed as discourses are produced within specific contexts and cannot be understood apart from them (Fairclough and Wodak 1997).

Legislative and political texts will be analyzed, as well as online consultation documents and presentations texts from seminars and conferences agencies associated with these schools. Additionally, ethnographic studies will be held in four MES selected on the basis of history and previous function in order to highlight the variation in collective social imaginary of the educational community of each school.

Ethnography is regarded as a science of "cultural description" (Wolcott, 1975) which can offer many advantages in understanding social contexts. The richness of ethnography resides in the fact that it is concerned with the daily experiences of people, how they interact together, how they make sense of their own situation. It allows the researcher to get close to the phenomenon under study, rather than emphasizing distance under the assumption of objectivity. And, this is what gives ethnography its power (Gerin – Lajoie, 1987).

With this mixed- method approach we will try to combine a macro-analysis at the level of institutions and policies implemented by Critical Narrative Analysis with a micro-analysis at the school level through ethnographic observation and personal involvement in the educational communities of these schools.

Conclusions, Expected Outcomes or Findings

The combination of Model and Experimental Schools in one entity, according to recent law of 2011 in Greece, gave the opportunity to investigate some really very interesting issues concerning the entire educational system. According to the historical view of Model-Experimental Schools, some expected outcomes of this research could be:

-The reveal of several subtle aspects of the special status of these schools. It consists of descriptions in depth concerning the

specific characteristics of educational personnel, students, infrastructure and other facilities aiming at excellent achievements and results.

-The existing differentiation compared with other schools. It consists of experimentation in several sectors (evaluation of school books, teaching methods, teachers' training etc.).

-The hidden parents' expectations of these schools. It will be great importance to see if the parents' expectations and beliefs will be in accordance with the aims of MES rising from the law of 2011.

-The probable and different educational social collective imaginary, covered inside the Greek community but acting in a special manner. We suppose that the history and the previous operation of each school (as Model or as Experimental) influences the social collective imaginary of their educational communities.

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Intent of Publication

This study aims to illuminate subtle aspects of the special status of Model –Experimental Schools (MES) in Greece by using a Critical Narrative Analysis to decompose legislative and political texts, as well as online consultation documents and presentations texts from seminars and conferences agencies associated with these schools. Additionally, we suppose that the differentiation of the history and the previous operation of each school as Model or as Experimental form a different educative social collective imaginary in each school which is expected to be revealed by an ethnographic approach.